

Block Diagonalization for Interference Mitigation in Ka-band Backhaul Networks

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Abstract—This paper considers the design of precoding and decoding techniques for backhaul networks at Ka band. In this frequency band, large antenna arrays must be employed with appropriate beamforming and precoding techniques to combat the high path loss. Traditional multi-antenna systems use digital baseband beamforming and precoding that is not economical for large antenna arrays due to its cost and power consumption. Recently, hybrid analog-digital solutions were suggested for millimeter wave multiple-input-multiple-output systems. They rely on two steps. The first step consists of an analog only beamforming which aims at the exploitation of the high antenna gain offered by the large-scale antenna array. The second step mitigates the multiuser interference by means of digital precoding. In this paper, we focus on the second step of the hybrid precoding. We propose a solution for interference mitigation in multi-base station scenarios. Our solution is based on a block diagonalization technique and requires full channel state information at each base station of a backhaul network. The performance of the algorithm is compared to a partial block diagonalization which was originally proposed for the single base station downlink scenario.

Keywords—backhaul networks; multiple base-station scenario; interference mitigation; hybrid beamforming; block diagonalization, SVD-based precoding

I. INTRODUCTION

The change in user trends and the appearance of new applications in recent years resulted in a huge increase of mobile traffic worldwide. Different access network technologies such as millimeter wave access, heterogeneous networks or massive MIMO have been proposed and are being currently investigated for such traffic increments.

In this paper we assume a backhaul network scenario followed by the EU H2020 project SANSA (Grant agreement no. 645047). This project is focused on providing a solution for the backhaul network of future communication systems to serve the increasing traffic demand. The SANSA solution is based on the development of disruptive enabling technologies for building a self-organizing hybrid terrestrial satellite backhaul network capable of reconfiguring the terrestrial topology and jointly exploiting the terrestrial and satellite links. The SANSA project aims at development of novel smart beamforming antennas, dynamic radio resource management and data-based shared access techniques for enabling the spectrum sharing among terrestrial and satellite segments in Ka band.

In this frequency band, high quality terrestrial communication links require large antenna arrays that provide high array gains. Conventional beamforming/precoding techniques are performed in the baseband (BB) by means of digital signal processing. The digitally precoded signals are up-converted into the passband and connected through radio frequency (RF) chains to all elements of the antenna array. However, large antenna arrays in terrestrial links at Ka-band would require hundreds of RF chains. This is infeasible due to high implementation costs and energy consumption. Analog beamforming/precoding would be a more economical solution, but it usually suffers from the constraint of the constant amplitude [1]. Therefore, the performance of analog beamforming/precoding is worse in comparison to the digital one. To achieve better performance, hybrid analog-digital solutions were suggested e.g. in [2], [4] and [5].

A single user hybrid beamforming (BF) was described in [2]. A solution for hybrid precoding at the base station (BS) transmitting data streams to multiple users with analog only combining was presented in [4]. Multiuser full-hybrid BF was described in [5]. All these hybrid BF solutions rely on a two stage approach, where in the first stage an analog only BF is performed. It aims at the high antenna gain offered by the large antenna array. The goal of the second stage is the mitigation of the multiuser interference by means of digital precoding.

Within this paper we focus on the second stage of the hybrid beamforming/precoding. We propose a solution for interference mitigation in multiple base-station multi-stream scenarios. The approach is based on Block Diagonalization (BD), firstly described in [2] for multiuser interference mitigation in the single base-station downlink scenario. In [5], the conventional BD was used for hybrid BF in the second digital stage for multiuser interference mitigation in single base-station downlink scenario. This paper generalizes the BD approach for multiuser interference mitigation in multiple BS scenarios using hybrid BF/precoding techniques. The proposed approach relies on the knowledge of channel state information (CSI) available at all BSs. As digital precoding is performed in the second stage of the hybrid BF approach, the amount of CSI is drastically reduced by the first analog stage. The analog BF reduces the amount of CSI knowledge related to the large number of antenna elements to the knowledge of the effective channel which is related to the number of RF chains. This makes our assumption of complete “effective CSI” available at each BS of a backhaul network feasible.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

A. System model

Consider a backhaul network with K transmitting base stations (TBS) and K receiving base stations (RBS). Each TBS and RBS is employed with N_A antennas. Assume that each TBS sends N_S data streams to each RBS.

The signal transmitted from the i -th TBS $\mathbf{x}_i \in \mathbb{C}^{N_A \times 1}$ is

$$\mathbf{x}_i = \tilde{\mathbf{F}}_i \mathbf{F}_i \mathbf{s}_i, \quad (1)$$

where vector $\mathbf{s}_i \in \mathbb{C}^{KN_S \times 1}$ contains KN_S data streams of the i -th TBS that are precoded by the BB precoding matrix $\mathbf{F}_i \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{RF} \times KN_S}$ and the RF precoding matrix $\tilde{\mathbf{F}}_i \in \mathbb{C}^{N_A \times N_{RF}}$. The signal received by the j -th RBS $\mathbf{r}_j \in \mathbb{C}^{N_A \times 1}$ is a sum of signals transmitted from all TBSs

$$\mathbf{r}_j = \sum_{i=1}^K \mathbf{H}_{ij} \tilde{\mathbf{F}}_i \mathbf{F}_i \mathbf{s}_i + \mathbf{n}_j, \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{H}_{ij} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_A \times N_A}$ is a channel matrix which describes a narrowband flat fading channel between the i -th TBS and the j -th RBS at a specific frequency, and $\mathbf{n}_j \in \mathbb{C}^{N_A \times 1}$ is a vector of i.i.d. noise, modelled by a zero-mean circularly symmetric complex Gaussian distribution process with variance σ_n^2 .

Define the transmit multiuser channel matrix $\mathbf{H}_j \in \mathbb{C}^{N_A \times KN_A}$ which is related to the j -th RBS as

$$\mathbf{H}_j = [\mathbf{H}_{1j}, \mathbf{H}_{2j}, \dots, \mathbf{H}_{Kj}] \quad (3)$$

and the BB multiuser precoding matrix $\mathbf{F} \in \mathbb{C}^{KN_{RF} \times KKN_S}$ as

$$\mathbf{F} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{F}_1 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & \mathbf{F}_2 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & \mathbf{F}_K \end{bmatrix}, \quad (4)$$

the received signal \mathbf{r}_j is given by

$$\mathbf{r}_j = \mathbf{H}_j \tilde{\mathbf{F}} \mathbf{F} \mathbf{s} + \mathbf{n}_j, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, K, \quad (5)$$

where the RF multiuser precoding matrix $\tilde{\mathbf{F}} \in \mathbb{C}^{KN_A \times KN_{RF}}$ has a block diagonal form similar to \mathbf{F} , and the vector $\mathbf{s} \in \mathbb{C}^{KKN_S \times 1}$ contains the data streams from all K TBSs

$$\mathbf{s} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{s}_1 \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{s}_K \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} [\mathbf{s}_{11}^T & \dots & \mathbf{s}_{1K}^T]^T \\ \vdots \\ [\mathbf{s}_{K1}^T & \dots & \mathbf{s}_{KK}^T]^T \end{bmatrix}, \quad (6)$$

where $\mathbf{s}_{ij} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_S \times 1}$ is a vector containing data streams that are transmitted from the i -th TBS to the j -th RBS. The received signal processed at the j -th RBS $\mathbf{y}_j \in \mathbb{C}^{KN_S \times 1}$ is given by

$$\mathbf{y}_j = \mathbf{W}_j^H \tilde{\mathbf{W}}_j^H \mathbf{H}_j \tilde{\mathbf{F}} \mathbf{F} \mathbf{s} + \mathbf{W}_j^H \tilde{\mathbf{W}}_j^H \mathbf{n}_j, \quad (7)$$

where $\tilde{\mathbf{W}}_j \in \mathbb{C}^{N_A \times N_{RF}}$ is the RF decoding matrix and $\mathbf{W}_j \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{RF} \times KN_S}$ is the BB decoding matrix of the j -th RBS. The form of the vector \mathbf{y}_j is described by

$$\mathbf{y}_j = [\mathbf{y}_{1j}^T \quad \dots \quad \mathbf{y}_{Kj}^T]^T, \quad (8)$$

where $\mathbf{y}_{ij} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_S \times 1}$ is a vector containing received data streams at the j -th RBS from the i -th TBS.

Received data streams processed by all RBSs $\mathbf{y} = [\mathbf{y}_1^T, \mathbf{y}_2^T, \dots, \mathbf{y}_K^T]^T \in \mathbb{C}^{KKN_S \times 1}$ are described by

$$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{W}^H \tilde{\mathbf{W}}^H \mathbf{H} \tilde{\mathbf{F}} \mathbf{F} \mathbf{s} + \mathbf{W}^H \tilde{\mathbf{W}}^H \mathbf{n}. \quad (9)$$

The vector $\mathbf{n} = [\mathbf{n}_1^T, \mathbf{n}_2^T, \dots, \mathbf{n}_K^T]^T \in \mathbb{C}^{KN_A \times 1}$ contains the noise from all receivers, and $\mathbf{W} \in \mathbb{C}^{KN_{RF} \times KKN_S}$ is the BB multiuser decoding matrix defined by

$$\mathbf{W} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{W}_1 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & \mathbf{W}_2 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & \mathbf{W}_K \end{bmatrix}. \quad (10)$$

$\tilde{\mathbf{W}} \in \mathbb{C}^{KN_A \times KN_{RF}}$ is the RF multiuser decoding matrix which has a block diagonal form similar to \mathbf{W} , and $\mathbf{H} \in \mathbb{C}^{KN_A \times KN_A}$ is a multiuser channel matrix defined by

$$\mathbf{H} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{H}_{11} & \mathbf{H}_{21} & \dots & \mathbf{H}_{K1} \\ \mathbf{H}_{12} & \mathbf{H}_{22} & \dots & \mathbf{H}_{K2} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \mathbf{H}_{1K} & \mathbf{H}_{2K} & \dots & \mathbf{H}_{KK} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (11)$$

As this work aims at a solution for the second stage of the hybrid beamforming/precoding, we define an equivalent multiuser channel matrix $\tilde{\mathbf{H}} \in \mathbb{C}^{KN_{RF} \times KKN_S}$ as

$$\tilde{\mathbf{H}} = \tilde{\mathbf{W}}^H \mathbf{H} \tilde{\mathbf{F}}. \quad (12)$$

Thus, the received data streams processed by all RBSs can be described by

$$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{W}^H \tilde{\mathbf{H}} \mathbf{F} \mathbf{s} + \mathbf{W}^H \tilde{\mathbf{n}}, \quad (13)$$

where $\tilde{\mathbf{n}} \in \mathbb{C}^{KN_A \times 1}$ is the noise after RF combining. According to (7) and (13), the vector \mathbf{y}_{ij} can be represented as a sum of the data streams from the i -th TBS to the j -th RBS, the interference and the noise after the BB combining at the j -th RBS,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{y}_{ij} &= \mathbf{W}_{ij}^H \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_{ij} \mathbf{F}_{ij} \mathbf{s}_{ij} \\ &+ \sum_{l=1}^K \sum_{\substack{k=1 \\ [k,l] \neq [i,j]}}^K \mathbf{W}_{ij}^H \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_{ij} \mathbf{F}_{lk} \mathbf{s}_{lk} + \mathbf{W}_j^H \tilde{\mathbf{n}}_j \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

where $\mathbf{F}_{ij} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{RF} \times N_S}$ represents a submatrix containing $((j-1)N_S + 1)$ to jN_S columns of \mathbf{F}_i . Thus, \mathbf{F}_{ij} incorporates vectors (its columns) for precoding of data streams \mathbf{s}_{ij} that are transmitted from the i -th TBS to the j -th RBS. Similarly, the matrix $\mathbf{W}_{ij} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{RF} \times N_S}$ represents a submatrix of $((i-1)N_S + 1)$ to iN_S columns of \mathbf{W}_j . The matrix \mathbf{W}_{ij} contains vectors (its columns) for decoding data streams transmitted from the i -th TBS to the j -th RBS. The interference covers all signals transmitted from the TBSs other than the targeted i -th TBS as well as signals transmitted from the i -th TBS but not intended for the j -th RBS.

The interference can be removed/ reduced by a proper design of precoding and decoding matrices \mathbf{F} and \mathbf{W} . Equation (13) is well known and used by a large number of precoding and decoding schemes. There exist various solutions related to different scenarios, such as the classical SVD-based precoding and decoding in multi-stream single user communication system. Unfortunately, these solutions cannot be directly used in the intended backhaul scenario due to the predefined form of the multiuser precoding (4) and decoding matrices (10) and due to the different power constraints in the intended scenario.

A partial solution is offered by the BD algorithm that was derived for a downlink MIMO scenario with one BS and

multiple users in [6]. By means of this algorithm, it is possible either to remove the interference from the data streams coming from the i -th TBS (downlink version of this BD algorithm with one TBS and multiple Rx users), or the interference from data streams intended for the j -th RBS (uplink version of this BD algorithm with multiple Tx users and one RBS). A straightforward implementation of the BD algorithm from [6] for hybrid BF/precoding was described in [5]. In section III, we show how can this algorithm be modified and extended to reduce overall interference described by the second term in (14).

B. Channel model

In this paper we rely on the clustered channel model described, e.g., in [2] or [3], where the channel matrix is defined as a sum of contributions from N_C scattering clusters, each of them containing N_P paths. This clustered channel model assumes path amplitudes that are modelled by i.i.d. zero mean circularly symmetric complex normal distributions. However, this does not realistically model backhaul links in Ka band having a strong LOS path and a rather small number of multipath components. Therefore, we handle the LOS path separately as follows

$$\mathbf{H} = \alpha_L G_T(\theta_{TL}, \varphi_{TL}) G_R(\theta_{RL}, \varphi_{RL}) \mathbf{v}_T(\theta_{TL}, \varphi_{TL}) \mathbf{v}_R(\theta_{RL}, \varphi_{RL})^H + \sum_{i=1, l=1}^{N_C N_P} \alpha_{i,l} G_T(\theta_{T i,l}, \varphi_{T i,l}) G_R(\theta_{R i,l}, \varphi_{R i,l}) \mathbf{v}_T(\theta_{T i,l}, \varphi_{T i,l}) \mathbf{v}_R(\theta_{R i,l}, \varphi_{R i,l})^H \quad (15)$$

Here, the antenna array at the transmitter and the receiver are described by the normalized array response vectors $\mathbf{v}_T(\theta_{T i,l}, \varphi_{T i,l})$ and $\mathbf{v}_R(\theta_{R i,l}, \varphi_{R i,l})$, respectively, at azimuth and elevation angles related to the corresponding path. $G_T(\theta_{T i,l}, \varphi_{T i,l})$ and $G_R(\theta_{R i,l}, \varphi_{R i,l})$ are antenna patterns of antenna elements within the antenna array at the transmitter and receiver, respectively. α_L is the complex amplitude of the LOS path that depends on the azimuth and elevation angles θ_{TL} , φ_{TL} , θ_{RL} , φ_{RL} . The angles together with the complex amplitude α_L are constants that are given by a priori known topology of the backhaul network. The complex amplitude α_L is defined by

$$\alpha_L = \frac{\lambda}{4\pi R} e^{j2\pi \frac{R}{\lambda}}, \quad (16)$$

which takes into account the path loss and the phase shift arising between two isotropic antennas situated at a distance R in free space. In our case, R is the distance between the reference antenna elements of the transmitting and receiving antenna array. The multipath amplitudes $\alpha_{i,l}$ are modelled by i.i.d. zero-mean circularly symmetric complex normal distributions with variance $\frac{|\alpha|^2}{4}$. The variance is simplistically defined by $\frac{|\alpha|^2}{4}$ which assures that the multipath magnitudes are smaller than the LOS path magnitude with very high probability.

III. BLOCK DIAGONALIZATION FOR INTERFERENCE MITIGATION

A. Assumptions

In order to elaborate a new solution that removes the interference from (14), consider a vector $\mathbf{y}_R \in \mathbb{C}^{KKNS \times 1}$ that contains all data streams received by the RBSs arranged in the following way

$$\mathbf{y}_R = [\mathbf{y}_{11}^T \dots \mathbf{y}_{1K}^T \mathbf{y}_{21}^T \dots \mathbf{y}_{2K}^T \dots \mathbf{y}_{K1}^T \dots \mathbf{y}_{KK}^T]^T. \quad (17)$$

Vector \mathbf{y}_R can be expressed as a linear combination of data streams \mathbf{s} using a notation of the transmission matrix $\mathbf{T} \in \mathbb{C}^{KKNS \times KKNS}$

$$\mathbf{y}_R = \mathbf{T}\mathbf{s} + \mathbf{n}_C, \quad (18)$$

where $\mathbf{n}_C \in \mathbb{C}^{KKNS \times 1}$ is the noise after combining at the RBSs. The transmission matrix \mathbf{T} is defined as

$$\mathbf{T} = \mathbf{W}_R^H \tilde{\mathbf{H}} \mathbf{F}, \quad (19)$$

where $\mathbf{W}_R \in \mathbb{C}^{KN_{RF} \times KKNS}$ is the rearranged decoding matrix, described by

$$\mathbf{W}_R = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{W}_{11} & \mathbf{0} & \dots & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{W}_{12} & \dots & \mathbf{0} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \dots & \mathbf{W}_{1K} \end{bmatrix} \dots \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{W}_{K1} & \mathbf{0} & \dots & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{W}_{K2} & \dots & \mathbf{0} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \dots & \mathbf{W}_{KK} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (20)$$

In order to remove the interference, it is necessary to diagonalize the transmission matrix \mathbf{T} . This is actually the main idea of the precoding and decoding in various communication systems.

If the number of streams N_S to be communicated between each pair of TBS and RBS is smaller than the rank R_{ij} of each channel $\tilde{\mathbf{H}}_{ij}$ (i.e. in our case $N_S < \min[R_{ij}]$), and the number of RF chains N_{RF} at each BS is larger than the maximum number of data streams that can be communicated over the multi-user channel $\tilde{\mathbf{H}}$ (i.e. in our case $N_{RF} > K \max[R_{ij}]$) then the diagonalization of the transmission matrix \mathbf{T} allows to allocate separate sub-channels for all KN_S data streams which avoids the disturbing interference.

B. Algorithm

The first step is the block diagonalization of the equivalent multi-user channel matrix $\tilde{\mathbf{H}}$. This is achieved by its pre-multiplication with null-space matrices $\mathbf{N}_F \in \mathbb{C}^{KN_{RF} \times KKNS}$ and $\mathbf{N}_W \in \mathbb{C}^{KN_{RF} \times KKNS}$ according to

$$\mathbf{H}_{BD} = \mathbf{N}_W^H \mathbf{H} \mathbf{N}_F, \quad (21)$$

where $\mathbf{H}_{BD} \in \mathbb{C}^{KKNS \times KKNS}$ is a block-diagonal channel matrix. The null-space matrix \mathbf{N}_F has the following form

$$\mathbf{N}_F = \begin{bmatrix} [\bar{\mathbf{N}}_{11} & \dots & \bar{\mathbf{N}}_{1K}] & \mathbf{0} & \dots & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & [\bar{\mathbf{N}}_{21} & \dots & \bar{\mathbf{N}}_{2K}] & \dots & \mathbf{0} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \dots & [\bar{\mathbf{N}}_{K1} & \dots & \bar{\mathbf{N}}_{KK}] \end{bmatrix}. \quad (22)$$

It contains orthogonal bases of null spaces $\mathbf{N}_{ij} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{RF} \times N_S}$ that are related to channel interference matrices $\tilde{\mathbf{H}}_{ij} \in \mathbb{C}^{(K-1)N_{RF} \times N_{RF}}$ defined by

$$\bar{\mathbf{H}}_{ij} = [\tilde{\mathbf{H}}_{i1}^T \dots \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_{i(j-1)}^T \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_{i(j+1)}^T \dots \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_{iK}^T]^T. \quad (23)$$

The channel interference matrices can be decomposed by means of SVD to

$$\bar{\mathbf{H}}_{ij} = \bar{\mathbf{U}}_{ij} \bar{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_{ij} \bar{\mathbf{V}}_{ij}^H = \bar{\mathbf{U}}_{ij} \bar{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_{ij} [\bar{\mathbf{V}}_{ij}^{(1)} \quad \bar{\mathbf{N}}_{ij}]^H, \quad (24)$$

where $\bar{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_{ij} \in \mathbb{C}^{(K-1)N_{RF} \times N_{RF}}$, $\bar{\mathbf{U}}_{ij} \in \mathbb{C}^{(K-1)N_{RF} \times (K-1)N_{RF}}$ and $\bar{\mathbf{V}}_{ij} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{RF} \times N_{RF}}$ are matrices containing singular values, left and right singular vectors, respectively. The rank \bar{R}_{ij} of the channel interference matrix $\bar{\mathbf{H}}_{ij}$ is equal to $\sum_{l=1, l \neq i}^K R_{lj}$. According to the previously stated assumptions about the minimum number of RF chains ($N_{RF} \geq K \max[R_{ij}]$) and the maximum number of data streams ($N_S \leq \min[R_{ij}]$) the rank of the channel interference matrix is $\bar{R}_{ij} \leq (K-1) \max[R_{ij}] = N_{RF} - \max[R_{ij}]$. Thus, $\bar{\mathbf{V}}_{ij}$ can be decomposed into two matrices $\bar{\mathbf{V}}_{ij}^{(1)} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{RF} \times (N_{RF} - N_S)}$ and $\bar{\mathbf{N}}_{ij} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{RF} \times N_S}$. The null-space matrix $\bar{\mathbf{N}}_{ij}$ contains right singular vectors related to the zero singular values in $\bar{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_{ij}$. Matrices $\bar{\mathbf{N}}_{ij}$ are used in (22) to create the null-space matrix \mathbf{N}_F .

The pre-multiplication of the channel matrix with the null space matrix \mathbf{N}_F does not completely block-diagonalize the transmission matrix \mathbf{T} . The null-space matrix $\bar{\mathbf{N}}_{ij}$ does not form the null space for equivalent channel matrices $\hat{\mathbf{H}}_{ij}$ which appears K times in each block-column of the transmission matrix \mathbf{T} . One of these entries is at the block-diagonal of \mathbf{T} and it is the desired transmission of the data streams from the i -th TBS to the j -th RBS, i.e. from \mathbf{s}_{ij} to \mathbf{y}_{ij} . The other $(K-1)$ entries represent interference from the other $(K-1)$ TBSs (accept the i -th TBS) to the j -th RBS. In order to remove this remaining interference, the equivalent multi-user channel matrix $\hat{\mathbf{H}}$ must be pre-multiplied with another null-space matrix \mathbf{N}_W according to (21). The null-space matrix \mathbf{N}_W is described by

$$\mathbf{N}_W = \begin{bmatrix} [\hat{\mathbf{N}}_{11} \dots \hat{\mathbf{N}}_{1K}] & \mathbf{0} & \dots & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & [\hat{\mathbf{N}}_{21} \dots \hat{\mathbf{N}}_{2K}] & \dots & \mathbf{0} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \dots & [\hat{\mathbf{N}}_{K1} \dots \hat{\mathbf{N}}_{KK}] \end{bmatrix}. \quad (25)$$

It contains orthogonal bases of null spaces $\hat{\mathbf{N}}_{ij} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{RF} \times N_S}$ that are related to channel interference matrices $\hat{\mathbf{H}}_{ij} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{RF} \times (K-1)N_{RF}}$ defined by

$$\hat{\mathbf{H}}_{ij} = [\hat{\mathbf{H}}_{1j} \dots \hat{\mathbf{H}}_{(i-1)j} \hat{\mathbf{H}}_{(i+1)j} \dots \hat{\mathbf{H}}_{Kj}]. \quad (26)$$

The channel interference matrices $\hat{\mathbf{H}}_{ij}$ can be decomposed by means of SVD to

$$\hat{\mathbf{H}}_{ij} = \hat{\mathbf{U}}_{ij} \hat{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_{ij} \hat{\mathbf{V}}_{ij}^H = [\hat{\mathbf{U}}_{ij}^{(1)} \quad \hat{\mathbf{N}}_{ij}] \hat{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_{ij} \hat{\mathbf{V}}_{ij}^H, \quad (27)$$

where $\hat{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_{ij} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{RF} \times (K-1)N_{RF}}$, $\hat{\mathbf{U}}_{ij} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{RF} \times N_{RF}}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{V}}_{ij} \in \mathbb{C}^{(K-1)N_{RF} \times (K-1)N_{RF}}$ are matrices containing singular values, left and right singular vectors, respectively. The rank considerations of the channel interference matrix $\hat{\mathbf{H}}_{ij}$ are the same as in the case of the channel interference matrix $\bar{\mathbf{H}}_{ij}$ discussed above. Thus, $\hat{\mathbf{U}}_{ij}$ can be decomposed into two matrices $\hat{\mathbf{U}}_{ij}^{(1)} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{RF} \times (N_{RF} - N_S)}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{N}}_{ij} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{RF} \times N_S}$. The null-space matrix $\hat{\mathbf{N}}_{ij}$ contains left singular vectors related to the

zero singular values in $\hat{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_{ij}$. Matrices $\hat{\mathbf{N}}_{ij}$ are used in (25) to create the null-space matrix \mathbf{N}_W .

The pre-multiplication of the equivalent multi-user channel matrix $\hat{\mathbf{H}}$ with the null-space matrices \mathbf{N}_F and \mathbf{N}_W according to (21) results in an equivalent block-diagonal channel matrix $\tilde{\mathbf{H}}_{BD}$. Its structure which is given by

$$\tilde{\mathbf{H}}_{BD} = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{N}}_{11}^H \mathbf{H}_{11} \bar{\mathbf{N}}_{11} & \mathbf{0} & \dots & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \hat{\mathbf{N}}_{12}^H \mathbf{H}_{12} \bar{\mathbf{N}}_{12} & \dots & \mathbf{0} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \dots & \hat{\mathbf{N}}_{KK}^H \mathbf{H}_{KK} \bar{\mathbf{N}}_{KK} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (28)$$

allocates all data stream transmissions (from \mathbf{s}_{ij} to \mathbf{y}_{ij}) separate sub-channels that are described by their BD equivalent channel matrices $\tilde{\mathbf{H}}_{BD ij} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_S \times N_S}$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{H}}_{BD ij} = \hat{\mathbf{N}}_{ij}^H \mathbf{H}_{ij} \bar{\mathbf{N}}_{ij}. \quad (29)$$

This enables exploitation of conventional precoding techniques designed for multi-stream single user scenarios to be applied in separation of multiple data streams that are communicated between i -th TBS and j -th RBS.

In this paper we rely on the classical SVD based pre- and decoding [7]. By applying the SVD, the channel matrix $\tilde{\mathbf{H}}_{BD ij}$ can be written as

$$\tilde{\mathbf{H}}_{BD ij} = \tilde{\mathbf{U}}_{ij} \tilde{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_{ij} \tilde{\mathbf{V}}_{ij}^H, \quad (30)$$

where $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_{ij} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_S \times N_S}$, $\tilde{\mathbf{U}}_{ij} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_S \times N_S}$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{V}}_{ij} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_S \times N_S}$ are matrices containing singular values, and the left and right singular vectors, respectively. The right singular vectors $\tilde{\mathbf{V}}_{ij}$ and the left singular vectors $\tilde{\mathbf{U}}_{ij}$ are used together with the null space matrices $\bar{\mathbf{N}}_{ij}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{N}}_{ij}$ defined by (24) and (27), respectively, to diagonalize the transmission matrix \mathbf{T} . This is done by the BB precoding at i -th TBS using the precoding matrix \mathbf{F}_i defined by

$$\mathbf{F}_i = [\bar{\mathbf{N}}_{i1} \tilde{\mathbf{V}}_{i1} \dots \bar{\mathbf{N}}_{iK} \tilde{\mathbf{V}}_{iK}] \boldsymbol{\Lambda}_i^{1/2}, \quad (31)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\Lambda}_i$ is a diagonal matrix whose elements λ_{ij} scale the power transmitted by each precoder \mathbf{F}_i at the i -th TBS. The optimal power loading can be found using the water-filling technique. At the receiver side, each j -th RBS uses BB combiners given by

$$\mathbf{W}_j = [\tilde{\mathbf{N}}_{1j} \tilde{\mathbf{U}}_{1j} \dots \tilde{\mathbf{N}}_{Kj} \tilde{\mathbf{U}}_{Kj}]. \quad (32)$$

These definitions of BB precoders and combiners indicate that full CSI is needed at each TBS and RBS. This is feasible thanks to the analog BF, which reduces huge CSI related to the large number of antenna elements to CSI of an effective channel which is related to the number of RF chains.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

The performance of the proposed BD algorithm for interference mitigation in multi BS backhaul network was evaluated by means of its achievable average rate per link. Its performance was compared to the performance of the BD algorithm from [6] which was derived for a downlink multiuser scenario and was applied in [5] to mitigate multiuser interference within the BB precoding stage of the hybrid precoding.

The achievable link rate can be defined for our system model, similarly to [2] and [5], by

$$S_{ij} = \log_2 \left(\mathbf{I}_{N_S} + \frac{P}{N_S} \mathbf{R}_{ij}^{-1} \mathbf{W}_{ij}^H \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_{ij} \mathbf{F}_{ij} \mathbf{F}_{ij}^H \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_{ij}^H \mathbf{W}_{ij} \right), \quad (33)$$

where P is the transmitted signal power and \mathbf{R}_{ij} is the interference and noise covariance matrix after BB combining, given by

$$\mathbf{R}_{ij} = \sum_{k=1}^K \sum_{l=1}^K \sum_{[k,l] \neq [i,j]} \mathbf{W}_{kl}^H \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_{kl} \mathbf{F}_{kl} \mathbf{F}_{kl}^H \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_{kl}^H \mathbf{W}_{kl} + \sigma_{n_j}^2 \mathbf{W}_j^H \mathbf{W}_j. \quad (34)$$

Here, $\sigma_{n_j}^2$ is the noise power at the j -th RBS.

For computation of link rates, the precoding and decoding matrices \mathbf{F}_i and \mathbf{W}_i , respectively, related to i -th TBS/RBS were normalized so that their squared Frobenius norm is equal to the number of data streams per link ($\|\mathbf{F}_i\|_F^2 = N_S$ and $\|\mathbf{W}_i\|_F^2 = N_S$). The equivalent channel matrix $\tilde{\mathbf{H}}_{ij}$ was normalized as well so that $\|\tilde{\mathbf{H}}_{ij}\|_F = N_{RF}$.

For the performance evaluation of the proposed BD algorithm we have assumed a ring topology of a backhaul network with 3 TBSs and 3 RBSs equidistantly situated along a circle with 5 km diameter as shown in Fig. 1. Each TBS was communicating 3 data streams to each RBS ($N_S = 3$). Thus, there are 9 communication links with 27 data streams in our scenario.

Fig. 1 Ring topology of the simulated backhaul network scenario

The equivalent channel was modeled according to (15) with three clusters and 1 path per cluster. Since our application scenario aims at smart reconfigurable backhaul networks, we assumed uniform circular antenna arrays that can cover 360° in azimuth. The number of RF chains N_{RF} was set to 15. This fulfilled the constriction given by the maximum rank of equivalent channel matrices $N_{RF} \geq K \max[R_{ij}]$ where $K \max[R_{ij}]$ was equal to 12 for 3 RBSs and channels with one strong LOS and 3 additional multipath components.

The first step of the proposed interference mitigation algorithm is to apply BD to the transmission matrix \mathbf{T} given by (19). An example of the transmission matrix after the proposed BD is illustrated in Fig. 2 in a logarithmical scale. The block diagonal structure is clearly visible. Each block represents sub-

channels that are ‘‘allocated’’ by the algorithm for the transmission of three data streams within one communication link from one TBS to another RBS. Due to the block diagonal structure of the transmission matrix there is no interference among the 9 communication links in the backhaul network scenario shown in Fig. 1. Each link can be treated as a single user transmission system with multiple streams.

Fig. 2 Block diagonalization of the normalized transmission matrix \mathbf{T}

Conventional precoding techniques designed for such multi-stream single user scenarios can be applied to separate multiple data streams within one communication link. In our simulation, we have used classical SVD based pre- and decoding described before. The result of the full diagonalization is illustrated in Fig. 3. Transmission of each data stream within our scenario has its own sub-channel and causes no interference to other data streams that are using its own sub-channels.

Fig. 3 Full diagonalization of the normalized transmission matrix \mathbf{T}

The performance of the proposed BD algorithm is compared to the performance of the BD algorithm from [5] and [6] which only partially makes the transmission matrix block diagonal in case of multi BS scenario. Fig. 4 shows the average link rate vs.

SNR for both algorithms. The average link rates were computed using 10000 realization of the effective channel matrix. SNR refers to the signal to noise ratio at the receiver. Since the backhaul links in Ka band aim at high data rates, we assume that high modulation orders are applied in such communication systems. High order modulation schemes require high SNR values at each RBS. Therefore, the SNR values used for the performance evaluation of the proposed algorithm spanned from 0 up to 50 dB.

Fig. 4 Average link rate of the proposed algorithm in comparison to partial BD algorithm.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper we consider a backhaul network scenario at Ka band. The network consists of multiple transmitting and receiving base stations. Each transmitting base station is supposed to transfer multiple data-streams to multiple receiving base stations using massive antenna arrays. Such scenarios require hybrid analog and digital precoding. The first step in conventional hybrid beamforming algorithms for mmWave systems presents the analog only beamforming that exploits the large antenna gain. The second step is the digital precoding for interference mitigation. We propose an extension of the block diagonalization algorithm for interference mitigation. In our backhaul scenario, the block diagonalization jointly mitigates the interference at the transmitting as well as the receiving base station. The philosophy behind this extension may seem to be straightforward, but the definition of the nulls space matrices is not straightforward and must be properly done using the interference matrices in order to allow the joint diagonalization

of the channel. Our extended block diagonalization algorithm is suitable for interference mitigation in multi BS multi stream scenarios. It relies on the knowledge of full channel state information. This assumption is justified by the effective channel that has drastically reduced dimensions in comparison to the radio frequency channel. The simulation results are compared to the conventional block diagonalization algorithm which only partially reduces the interference in the assumed scenario. In future work we want to relax the assumption of perfect channel state information required at each base station and analyze performance of the whole hybrid analog-digital system for a channel model taking into account different assumptions on line-of-sight and multipath components. Furthermore, our future work will aim at comparison our hybrid analog-digital approach based on block diagonalization interference mitigation to approaches that are known in the area of the interference alignment for MIMO X channels [8].

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Commission in the framework of SANSA (Grant agreement no. 645047)

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